

PROBLEMS WITH THE USE OF INNOVATION PROJECTS IN
THE HOTEL BUSINESS

Kunnazarova Orazxan

Karakalpak State University faculty of Economics

1st year Master student

Abstract. This article analyzes the issues of effective use of innovative ideas in modern hotel business, and the article is based on international experience.

Keywords: innovation, tourism, hotel, business, advanced technology, startup.

In the context of increasing competition in the global tourism market, new ideas are needed to increase the attractiveness of our country as a promising tourist destination, effective mechanisms for the development of tourism infrastructure and new innovative approaches to promoting Uzbekistan as an interesting tourist destination.

At the end of 2016, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the Decree “On measures to ensure the accelerated development of the tourism industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan,” which includes the creation and development of tourism infrastructure, simplification of visa procedures and provides for the creation of a Coordination Council for Tourism under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The creation of the Coordination Council will make it possible to coordinate tourism development activities between various ministries, departments and other business entities, as well as to quickly consider and resolve issues related to the development of tourism in the country.

Innovation and the development of new services are important strategic features to ensure growth and sustainable prosperity for every industry, but

especially for those industries where markets are saturated and customers select goods and services from around the world, such as in tourism. There are various definitions of the term innovation, which comes from the Latin word *innovatio*, which means the creation of something.

Innovation in the hotel industry is developing at a rapid pace. The reasons for this are as follows: to attract as many customers as possible, getting them interested in your hotel, your brand; win over the guest and thereby make him a regular customer; increase the profit of the enterprise.

Sheraton Roma in the Italian capital has always tried to be in the leading group of high-tech hotels. Its 640 rooms and suites are equipped with the most modern equipment. This time he was the first in the international hotel chain Sheraton to open an Internet cafe, from the terminals of which you can send video cards. Webcams will be installed in another 300 Sheraton hotels.

Four Seasons Resort on the island of Nevis offers its guests “adopt” a sea turtle: the hotel is participating in a special research program in which several dozen of these animals have been attached with a special transmitter that transmits information through a satellite surveillance system.

Many other hotels around the world note the need to refurbish rooms and introduce the latest electronic technologies, without which the modern world is simply unthinkable. If until recently, leading hoteliers note, clients paid more attention to the number of square meters of a room and household amenities, but now High-Tech is increasingly in demand. For example, the Peninsula Hotels chain conducts special research to study the demand and introduction of new technologies into the market. Thus, at The Peninsula Tokyo hotel, which opened on September 1, each room has a wireless bedside control panel for air temperature, lighting, blinds, alarm clock, telephone, and audio systems.

Restaurants in Europe, the USA and Japan are testing a new technology for ordering dishes using touch screens, designed to replace waiters who are not always polite and sometimes make mistakes. In addition to the fact that

electronic the menu helps reduce costs, it attracts to young customers, and enticing photographs of dishes serve as visual advertising to them.

In Israel, Conceptic has already begun installing e-Menu in sushi bars, pubs and family restaurants. The system is built on the basis of touch terminals. In addition to Israel, Conceptic systems are installed in restaurants in Belgium, France and South Africa.

Smart watches are not only about tracking steps and notifying you about incoming SMS or calls, but also a good way to improve your work efficiency. This can be confirmed by the prestigious hotel chain Viceroy Hotel Group, which has adopted the Samsung Gear S3.

The hotel chain provided all its employees with TIZEN devices. But they will not use them to obtain personal messages, but for prompt communication in order to provide hotel services faster and with better quality.

Amazon has presented a special version of its voice assistant for hotels - Alexa for Hospitality, which is currently being tested in Marriott hotels. The service is implemented on the basis of Echo smart speakers, which are installed in each room and are customized directly to the specifics and needs of a particular hotel facility.

This will allow hotels will simplify their service processes, and guests will have the opportunity to receive all the necessary information about the hotel and order services directly from their room.

For example, find out the location of the nearest fitness center, swimming pool opening hours, order lunch in your room or cleaning, and contact the concierge or reception.

For it will be enough to ask “Alexa, order wine” or “Alexa, reserve a place in the

SPA.” This request will be sent to an employee of the relevant department of the hotel.

Alexa could even replace your phone. Amazon demonstrated in a promotional video how a girl was able to call her children from her hotel room using only an Echo.

Figure 3: Alexa for Hospitality

The use and implementation of data and other innovations helps improve the quality of service, increase the competitiveness and image of the hotel, making it unique. With the help of innovations correctly introduced into the hotel, the number of regular customers will increase significantly. A guest, when leaving a hotel, should leave it only with pleasant emotions, emphasizing for himself the important factors that are only available in this hotel.

Based on the above findings, we offer the following recommendations for the development of innovative hotels:

- Gaining experience in introducing innovative technologies following the example of the most advanced foreign countries;
- Implementation of innovative projects developed in our country;
- pay attention to the development of innovative ideas in the field of tourism;
- Use of innovative technologies in the hotel industry;
- To establish cooperation between universities and tourism entities in the field of introducing innovative technologies.

References:

1. Grebenkova Y.V. INNOVATIONS IN THE HOTEL BUSINESS // Modern high technology. – 2013. – No. 10-2. – pp. 247-247;
2. URL: <http://www.top-technologies.ru/ru/article/viewid=33457> (access date: 01/19/2019).

